

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF STRUGGLE, ONE OF OUR NATIONAL VALUES, IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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***Annotation:** This article provides information about the prospects of the Uzbek national wrestling and its role in the education of young people, as well as the prestige of today's wrestling on the world stage, as well as information about the education of students as modern professionals.*

***Keywords:** Independence, perspective, continent, arena, federation, International Wrestling Association, Universiade.*

Since independence, Uzbekistan has paid special attention to physical culture and sports, and at the same time, the Uzbek wrestling, recognized as our national sport, has always been characteristic of the spirit and original qualities of our people: courage, courage, the philosophy of tolerance, nobility, honesty, humanity is embodied in relation to the enemy.

Thanks to our independence, today we are looking for tasks that correspond to the highest goals. Thanks to national independence, Uzbek wrestling spreads its wings on the world sports arenas. It is important to see that the principles of the idea of national independence are embodied in the essence of the philosophy of struggle, which has been formed over the centuries. It is quite natural that kurash was born together with the Uzbek people and lived with them, so this value, so to speak, the pearl of the spirituality of our nationally independent people, has spread to seven climates.

In fact, he brought the world the independence of Uzbekistan and the struggle for national independence. Wrestling, as a tradition and national value of the Uzbek people, has spread to distant countries on all continents of the world.

Wrestling is one of the heritage values left from our ancestors, which has an important impact on the spiritual and moral education of the Uzbek people, as well as on the education of young people. Its beauty lies in the fact that it has been formed and improved over the centuries, its beliefs have been in harmony with the universal philosophy, it has become one of the main points of the spirituality and mentality of our people. Today we can find thousands of fans of Uzbek wrestling in more than 140 countries on five continents, including Canada, Bolivia, Brazil, South Africa, Great Britain, the Netherlands, Turkey, India, Thailand, Japan.

Even enthusiastic residents of the Dominican Republic, Paraguay, Equator, Zambia, Nigeria and the Mauritius Islands, which are considered “alien” in the eyes of Uzbeks, are well aware of Uzbek kurash. Naturally, they learn the secrets of wrestling and competition techniques with great interest and enthusiasm.

To date, regional federations have been established in America, Africa, Europe and Asia. They are currently expanding their reach to promote this popular ancient sport.

Currently, the National Wrestling Federations of more than 50 countries of the world are considered full members of the International Wrestling Association. Such sports organizations are on the threshold of official registration in more than 30 other countries. The composition of the Executive Committee of the International Wrestling Association is practically formed.

This word, spoken with passion and pride, justifies itself today. Commendable work is being done to develop and popularize Uzbek wrestling, especially in India and the UK. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. This initiative, put forward by Karimov, was put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, an ideological follower of I. Karimov, with the main goal of including national wrestling in the program of the Olympic Games.

Based on this, the training of highly qualified personnel (students, talented athletes, young coaches and specialists) is one of the most important issues. That is

why a special place in these problems is occupied by the development and improvement of the system for training talented student wrestlers, their selection and education.

In particular, the sports games "Universiade", organized among student-athletes of higher educational institutions of our Republic, which received the status of a small Olympiad in our country, as well as holding various sports competitions on various topics and the presence of wrestling competitions in the program of these competitions, are important for talented wrestlers, a sign that a great opportunity for growth in quantity and quality is being created.

Working with talented student wrestlers is both easy and difficult at the same time. In fact, they differ from their peers in their political integrity, search for truth, awareness, and intelligence. The difficulty is that they require teachers to have a sense of responsibility for working with each athlete as a person.

It is necessary to know that purposeful, systematic work must be carried out with such working students and a system of special educational processes must be organized for them. Experiments show that the work done in this direction in some sports (national wrestling) gives good results. For example, student wrestling competitions are regularly held in our republic. For many years, students of higher educational institutions have been participating in such sports competitions and taking pride of place. Achievements are growing day by day in quantitative and qualitative terms. This indicates that work in the field of physical culture is well organized in higher educational institutions.

Therefore, the holding of sports contests by higher educational institutions and educational institutions, especially of the city, regional and republican scale, is not without benefit. Because in these events the level of training of athletes, the independence and deep thinking of the pupils are formed, the feeling of craving for wrestling continues to develop, which is an integral part of our national value.

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